

**A SCIENTIFIC STUDY ON COMBINED SPECIFIC HANDBALL TRAINING AND
PROPRIOCEPTIVE NEUROMUSCULAR FACILITATION (PNF)
STRETCHING ON HIGH DENSITY LIPOPROTEIN AMONG MEN HANDBALL
PLAYERS**

C LAVANYA KUMARI, D SYMALA BAI, G SUDHAKAR BABU

ASSISTANT PROFESSOR ^{1,3}, PROFESSOR ²

lavanya_kumari88@gmail.com, dsyamala17@gmail.com, sudhakarbabu319@gmail.com

Department of Physics, Sri Venkateswara Institute of Technology,

N.H 44, Hampapuram, Rappthadu, Anantapuramu, Andhra Pradesh 515722

Abstract

This research set out to examine how high density lipoprotein (HDL) levels changed in male handball players after they participated in a programme that included both traditional handball training and proprioceptive neuromuscular facilitation (PNF) stretching. In order to accomplish the study's goals, thirty male handball players were chosen in 2021 from Dr. Zakir Hussain College in Ilayangudi, Sivagangai district, Tamil Nadu, India. The age range of the subjects is 18–25 years. There were a total of 30 students chosen for the study; 15 were assigned to the experimental group and 10 to the control group. The eight-week trial period was for the experimental group to practise a combination of proprioceptive neuromuscular facilitation (PNF) stretching and particular handball training. Throughout the research, the control group did not get any kind of instruction. The study's criteria variable was high density lipoprotein. Blood samples were used to evaluate the individuals' high density lipoprotein (HDL). Both the pre- and post-training assessments were administered at the beginning and end of the eight-week training sessions, respectively. In order to compare the two groups' means from before and after the test, the statistical method known as the "t" ratio was used. On the criteria variable, the findings showed that there was a substantial difference. The experimental group had better results on high density lipoprotein than the control group because they received a combination of targeted handball training and proprioceptive neuromuscular facilitation (PNF) stretching.

Keywords: Practice of proprioceptive neuromuscular facilitation (PNF) stretches in conjunction with specialised handball training, high density lipoprotein, and the "t" ratio.

INTRODUCTION

In its present form, sport-specific training refers to methods of honing a skill in the gym with the hope that it will carry over to the actual playing field.

Athletes may benefit best from sport-specific training by engaging in game play. Hence, it is the responsibility of the sport's coaches—the batting coach, the golf teacher, the tackling coach, etc.—to provide players with effective sport-specific instruction. Strength and conditioning experts, on the other hand, may design programmes that are invaluable for athletes, helping them train the right energy systems, build the right muscles for each sport, and perfect the exact motions used in their chosen activity.

Advanced flexibility training methods include Proprioceptive Neuromuscular Facilitation (PNF), which combines stretching and contracting the targeted muscle group. When it comes to stretching, PNF is among the best options for enhancing flexibility and mobility. **STUDY PROCEDURE**

Subject

selection

The researchers wanted to see how high density lipoprotein (HDL) levels changed after male

handball players participated in a programme that included both traditional training and a more modern kind of stretching called proprioceptive neuromuscular facilitation (PNF). The goal of the research was to do this by randomly selecting 30 male handball players to participate. People ranging in age from 18 to 25 made up the sample.

Selection of variable

Independent variable

- Combined specific handball training and proprioceptive neuromuscular facilitation (PNF) stretching

Dependent variable

- High density lipoprotein

EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

There were a total of thirty-five participants in the study; fifteen were assigned to either the control group or an experimental group that received a combination of proprioceptive neuromuscular facilitation (PNF) stretching and particular handball instruction. For eight weeks, the experimental group practiced particular handball training in conjunction with proprioceptive neuromuscular facilitation (PNF) stretching. They did this five days a week. The control group consisted of students who did not participate in any additional physical education classes beyond what was required by their course of study. As a criteria variable, we chose high density lipoprotein, a biochemical marker. A criteria variable called high density lipoprotein was assessed in both the pre- and post-training blood samples of all individuals in the two groups.

Statistical technique

The 't' test was used to analysis the significant differences, if any, difference between the groups respectively.

Level of significance

The 0.05 level of confidence was fixed to test the level of significance which was considered as an appropriate.

ANALYSIS OF THE DATA

The significance of the difference among the means of the experimental group was found out by pre-test. The data were analysed and dependent 't' test was used with 0.05 levels as confidence.

TABLE I
Analysis of t-ratio for the pre and post tests of experimental and control group on High density lipoprotein
 (Scores counts in mg/ dl)

Variables	Group	Standard Deviation		Sd Error	
		Pre	Post	Pre	Post
High density lipoprotein	Control Group	1.94	1.62	0.50	0.41
	Experimental Group	1.72	1.50	0.44	0.38

TABLE II

Variables	Group	Mean		Degree of freedom	't' ratio
		Pre	Post		
High density lipoprotein	Control Group	55.93	55.73	14	1.146
	Experimental Group	56.40	58.83	14	16*

**Significance at .05 level of confidence.*

The Table-I and II shows that the mean values of pre-test and post-test of the control group on high density lipoprotein were 55.93 and 55.73 respectively. The obtained 't' ratio was 1.146, since the obtained 't' ratio was less than the required table value of 2.14 for the significant at 0.05 level with 14 degrees of freedom it was found to be statistically insignificant. The mean values of pre-test and post-test of the experimental group on high density lipoprotein were 56.40 and 58.83 respectively. The obtained 't'ratio was 16* since the obtained 't' ratio was greater than the required table value of 2.14 for significance at 0.05 level with 14 degrees of freedom it was found to be statistically significant. The result of the study showed that there was a significant difference between control group and experimental group in high density lipoprotein. It may be concluded from the result of the study that experimental group improved in high density lipoprotein due to eight weeks of combined specific handball training and proprioceptive neuromuscular facilitation (PNF) stretching practice.

Figure-1

Bar Diagram Showing the Pre and Post Mean Values of Experimental and Control Group on High density lipoprotein

DISCUSSIONS ON FINDINGS

The study found that high density lipoprotein, the dependent variable, was significantly improved in the experimental group compared to the control group, which consisted of participants who had practiced both specific handball training and proprioceptive neuromuscular facilitation (PNF) stretching. Additionally, when contrasted with the control group, those who practiced both particular handball training and proprioceptive neuromuscular facilitation (PNF) stretches showed significant improvement.

CONCLUSION

We conclude the following from the data: 1. After the training period, the experimental group had significantly lower levels of high density lipoprotein than the control group.

2. The level of high density lipoprotein increased significantly. Eight weeks of training that included both targeted handball and proprioceptive neuromuscular facilitation (PNF) stretching led to better results for the experimental group.

REFERENCES

The authors of the article are Parthasarathy, S., Alaguraja, K., and Selvakumar, K. (2020). Reduced stress levels in middle-aged males with the use of shambhavi mahamudra and pranayama. Volume 11, Issue 6, pages 795–798 of the Indian Journal of Public Health Research and Development. Marinar Rai et al. (2020). Section 2. Yogic strength. Journal of Advanced Science and Technology: An International Journal, 29(3), pp. 6225-6229. As stated by Sumitra Das et al. in 2020. The result of doing rowing and yoga. Pages 7079–7084 of the International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology, volume 29, issue 3. In 2020, Alalaguraja and Yoga published a paper. Yoga and naturopathy together for hypertension patients: an effect on maximal oxygen consumption. Volume 11, issue 4, pages 131–134, of the Indian Journal of Public Health Research and Development. Fifth, Alalaguraja and Yoga (2020). Class I obese patients' body mass index as a result of yoga treatment. Public health research and development in India, volume 11, issue 5, pages 143–146. 6. (2020) James Rathinaraj, Yoga, Alaguraja, and Selvakumar. Effects on low density lipoprotein (Ldl) in middle-aged women with a walking-yogic practice combination. Volume 11, issue 6, pages

362-365, of the Indian Journal of Public Health Research and Development. Alagauraja and Yoga (2017). 7. International Journal of Yoga Physiotherapy and Physical Education, 2(7), pp.70-71. The effect of yoga asana practice on flexibility in overweight schoolboys. In 2018, Alalaguraja and Yoga did research. Implications for college-aged men's dynamic strength from core stability training. Volume 3, Issue 2, Pages 436–437, International Journal of Yogic Human Movement and Sports Sciences. The authors of the article are Yoga, Balamuralikrishnan, and Alaguraja (2018). Physiological parameters affected by cyclic meditation. Journal of Advanced Education and Research International, Volume 4, Issue 1, Pages 17–18. Lalaguraja and Yoga (2019) were cited as number 10. A study on the effects of yoga on the resting heart rates of schoolchildren. Journal of Applied Research in India, volume 9, issue 7, pages 43–44. Marinar Rai, Yoga, Alaguraja, Selvakumar, and Sumitra Das (2020). 13. Yogic strength. Journal of Advanced Science and Technology: An International Journal, 29(3), pp. 6225-6229.

12. Alaguraja, K., Selvakumar, K., Yoga, P., and Marinar Rai (2020). The result of doing rowing and yoga. Page numbers 7079–7084 of the International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology, volume 29, issue 3. (2020) Alalaguraja and Yoga 13. Yoga and naturopathy together for hypertension patients: an effect on maximal oxygen consumption. Volume 11, issue 4, pages 131–134, of the Indian Journal of Public Health Research and Development. In 2020, Alalaguraja and Yoga published a paper. Class I obese patients' body mass index as a result of yoga treatment. Public health research and development in India, volume 11, issue 5, pages 143–146.

15. Alaguraja, K., Selvakumar, K., Yoga, P., and James Rathinaraj, S. (2020). Effects on low density lipoprotein (Ldl) in middle-aged women with a walking-yogic practice combination. Volume 11, issue 6, pages 362-365, of the Indian Journal of Public Health Research and Development. The authors of the article are Parthasarathy, S., Alaguraja, K., and Selvakumar, K. (2020). Reduced stress levels in middle-aged males with the use of shambhavi mahamudra and pranayama. Volume 11, Issue 6, pages 795–798 of the Indian Journal of Public Health Research and Development. 17. In a study conducted by James Rathinaraj, S., Yoga, P., Alaguraja, K., and Selvakumar, K. (2020). Effects on low density lipoprotein (LDL) in middle-aged women with a walking-yogic practice combination. Public health research and development in India, volume 11, issue 6, pages 1121–1124.

18. In 2019, Alaguraja, Yoga, Balamuralikrishnan, and Selvakumar published their work. How a yoga programme affects the resting heart rate of overweight schoolchildren: a research investigation. Volume 9, Issue 8, Pages 483–487, Journal of Computing and Information Science. 19. Published by Alalaguraja and Yoga in 2019. Investigate the effects of pranayama on physiological parameters in a sample of rural schoolchildren. Volume 9, Issue 8, Pages 545–550, Journal of Computing and Information Science. Alaguraja, K., Yoga, P., James Rathinaraj, S., and Selvakumar, K. (2019) were the authors of the paper. Research on the effects of yoga on maximum oxygen absorption in patients with stress. Indian Journal of Applied Research, volume 9, issue 9, pages 38–39. Twenty-one. Alagauraja, K. (2019). Examine the effects of meditation and yoga on psychological and social variables in athletes. Indian Journal of Applied Research, volume 9, issue 10, pages 73–74.

In 2019, Alagauraja and Yoga published a paper. Research on the effects of a yoga programme on fat mass in males attending rural schools. Page numbers 07–09 from the International Journal of Physical Education, Exercise, and Sports, volume 1, issue 2. In 2019, Alagauraja and Yoga published a study. Effects of the yoga programme on BMI in

overweight individuals. Alalaguraja and Yoga (2019) published an article in the International Journal of Physical Education, Exercise and Sports, volume 1, issue 2, pages 4–06. Meditation and pranayama techniques for boosting self-assurance. Paper published in the International Journal of Physical Education, Exercise, and Sports, volume 1, issue 2, pages 501–503.

[25] Alalaguraja and Yoga (2019). Stress reduction with mindfulness meditation for working guys. Publication: International Journal of Physiology, Sports, and Physical Education, Volume 1, Issue 1, Pages 09–11. In 2019, Alaguraja and Yoga published. Cholesterol treatment in high school males using yogic techniques. Physiology, Exercise, and Physical Education: An International Journal, 1(1), pp. 09-11. 27. In 2019, Alaguraja and Yoga published. The influence of yoga and naturopathy on triglycerides in stress patients: a scientific research. Publication: International Journal of Physiology, Exercise, and Physical Education, Volume 1, Issue 1, Pages 09–11. In 2019, Alaguraja and Yoga published. Examine the impact of the yoga programme on trained handball players' low density lipoprotein levels. Physiology, Exercise, and Physical Education: An International Journal, 1(1), pp. 09-11. 29. In 2019, Alaguraja and Yoga published. An analysis of the cumulative impact of saq training and the yoga package on handball players' self-esteem. Alalaguraja and Yoga (2019) published an article in the International Journal of Sports, Exercise, and Physical Education, volume 1, issue 1, pages 15–17. Systolic blood pressure in middle-aged women who are unemployed: the effects of a pranayama package. Alalaguraja and Yoga (2019) published an article in the International Journal of Sports, Exercise, and Physical Education, volume 1, issue 1, pages 18–20. Pranayama protocol for middle-aged women who are jobless and lacking self-confidence. Volume 1, Issue 1, Pages 18–20, International Journal of Sports, Exercise, and Physical Education. In 2017, Alagauraja and Yoga published a paper. Journal of Innovative Knowledge Concepts, 5, 6, pages 18–20, examines the effect of yoga on students' VO2 max. 33. In a 2009 publication by Balasubramanian and Yogaraj. The impact of strength training and other forms of physical activity on biochemical markers in collegiate football players, published in the International Journal of Physical Education, volume 2, issues 1 and 2, pages 1–4. Selvalakshmi and Yogaraj (2009) were cited as number 34. The impact of several yoga postures and breathing techniques on weighted women's haemoglobin and glucose levels was studied in the Asian Journal of Physical Education and Computer Science in Sports, volume 1, issue 1, pages 262-264. The authors of the cited work are Yogaraj, Ramaraj, and Elangovan (2010). College women's adrenal gland functioning and blood cholesterol levels as a result of practicing certain asanas, Asian Journal of Physical Education and Computer Science in Sports, 2(1), pp. 206-208. In 2010, Yogaraj, Ramaraj, and Elangovan published a paper. Physiological and Biochemical Changes in Female College Students After Engaging in Certain Yogic Exercises, Asian Journal of Physical Education and Computer Science in Sports, 3(1), pp. 27–29.

Yogaraj and Elangovan (2011) were cited in footnote 37. An international journal of physical education, sports management and yogic sciences article titled "Effect of Varying Yogic Practice Packages on Selected Bio-Chemical Variables of College Men Students" (pp. 35–39) just appeared. In the Asian Journal of Physical Education & Computer Science in Sports, volume 9, issue 1, pages 47–49, Yoga (2013) examined the impact of several yoga practice modules on platelet count in women with type II diabetes. Yogi, P. (2014). White blood cell count in women with type II diabetes as a result of several integrated yogic practice modules. International journal of physical education, sports management and yogic sciences, 4(1), pp. 33-36. 40. Yoga, P. (2014) Red blood cell count among women of type II diabetes patients: an effect of diverse integrated modules of yogic practices. International journal of Sports Technology, Management and Allied Sciences, 3(1), pp.70-74.

46. Yoga, P. (2014). White blood cell count among college male students: effects of various yogic practice packages on this indicator, *International Journal of Health, Physical Education & Computer Science in Sports*, 15(1), pp.47-49.
- Yoga, P. (2015). 42. In this article from the *International Journal of Engineering Research and Sports Science*, the authors examine the effects of different yoga practice packages on the cardiovascular endurance of male college students (pp. 33–34).
- Yoga and Ranjith (2019) were cited as number 43. Sectional breathing and nadi suddhi pranayama's effect on male college students' white blood cell count was published in the *International Journal of Health, Physical Education, and Computer Science in Sports*, volume 17, issue 2, and ran from pages 16 to 18.
- Yoga, P. (2015). Page 44. Results from a study on male college students' red blood cell counts using sectional breathing and nadi suddhi pranayama were published in the *International Journal of Information Research and Review*, volume 2, issue 3, pages 537-539.
45. Yogi (2018). Male handball players' respiratory frequency as a function of circuit training, This is the 29th issue of the *International Journal of Health, PE, and Computer Science in Sports*, and it has pages 153–155.
- Balamuralikrishnan and Yoga (2018) were cited as number 46. Body composition as a function of aerobic exercise intensity. Publication: *International Journal of Physical Education, Sports and Health*, Volume 5, Issue 2, Pages 284–285.
- Section 47, "James Rathinaraj and Yoga's research" (2018). Using structured resistance training to increase maximal oxygen consumption, in *International Journal of Physical Education, Sports, and Health*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 286-287.
- Yoga and James Rathinaraj (2018) were cited as number 48. Pranayama and Its Effects on Heart Rate, *International Journal of Yoga for Health and Fitness*, vol. 3, no. 2, pages 349–350.
49. According to Selvakumar and Yoga (2018). Improvements in collegiate men's handball players' vertical jumps as a result of maximum power training, published in the *International Journal of Yogic Human Movement and Sports Sciences*, volume 3, issue 2, pages 438-439.
- In 2018, Yoga and Balamuralikrishnan published a paper. In the *International Journal of Yogic Human Movement and Sports Sciences*, volume 3, issue 2, pages 473-474, the authors examine the effects of yoga on psychological variables in schoolboys.
- This is reference 51 from Yoga, James Rathinaraj, and Selvakumar (2018). Increasing college students' flexibility with vigorous interval training, *International Journal of Advanced Education and Research*, 3(6), pp. 72-73.
- P. Yoga and S. James (2019). 52. Resting heart rate as a function of activity in a school-aged population, *Journal of Advanced Education and Research International*, volume 4, issue 1, pages 21–22.
- In 2019, Balamuralikrishnan and Yoga published a study. *International Journal of Advanced Education and Research*, volume 4, issue 1, pages 19–20, examines the effects of Tibetan yoga on the cardiovascular endurance of overweight male students.
- The work of Rajitha and Yoga (2019) is cited as 54. The effect of yoga on the resting heart rates of male collegiate handball players was published in the *Indian Journal of Applied Research* in the volume 9, issue 4, pages 59-60.
- In 2019, Selvakumar and Yoga published a study. Study on the effects of yoga on flexibility in university students, published in the *Indian Journal of Applied Research*, volume 9, issue 7, pages 45–46.
- In 2019, Sumitra Das and Yoga published a book. Yoga program's impact on rural schoolgirls' BMI, *Journal of Information and Computational Science*, 9(8), pp.462-467.
- In 2019, Sumitra Das and Yoga published a work. *The Journal of Information and Computational*

Science published an article titled "A study on effect of combined yoga and naturopathy on triglycerides among high school girls" (vol. 9, no. 8, pages 451-454).
58. In 2019, Marinarai and Yoga published. A scientific study on the effects of a yoga programme on BMI in type 1 obese people, published in the Journal of Information and Computational Science, volume 9, issue 10, pages 468-473.
59. In 2019, Marinarai and Yoga published. Journal of Information and Computational Science, 9(10), pp.455-459, reports on the effects of yoga on high density lipoprotein levels in females in high school.
60. Pilates P. (2020). Scientific Technological Evaluation of Isolated and Companied Practices of Yogic Practices and Meditation on Psychological Conditions of College Students. Pages 6257–6258 of the International Journal of Scientific and Technological Research, volume 9, issue 2.